

Measuring Emotion and Attention by Analyzing Eye Properties

Jakob de Lemos – R&D, iMotions – Emotion Technology A/S, Copenhagen, Denmark, +45 3124 6588, jakob.de.lemos@imotionsglobal.com

Abstract

One important methodological problem in the study of emotion and attention within market research is the absence of fast, reliable, easy-to-use tools, which adds additional insight, is applicable on large sample sizes and practically possible to integrate into the methods used today. This paper introduces a new way of measuring emotional impact from advertisement and product design by analyzing subconscious reactions within the eyes. The technology is integrated in the analysis software Emotion Tool™, a diagnostic tool designed to measure immediate emotional responses on print advertisement, marketing material, design, packaging, magazine covers etc. The non-intrusive, non-verbal, psychophysiology measurement instrument measures the visual attention and emotional involvement to the advertisement and it determines if the emotion is of a pleasant or unpleasant character. Each emotional response is extracted from subtle dynamical psycho-physiological changes within the respondents' eye via a camera based eye tracker.

Conference theme: Design & Emotion: Methodological issues

Keywords: Emotions, emotional response, emotion technology, non-intrusive physiological measurements, visual attention, eye tracking, arousal, decision-making, behavior, consumer research, visual processing, design evaluation.

Introduction

Imagine you lose your keys inside a dark house! Would you then go outside to look for them because that's where the street lamp is on? Probably not! The behavior of looking for the keys outside are equivalent to the way traditional market researchers target the investigation and analysis of emotion and attention.

Because of the subconscious nature of emotions traditional methodology based on cognitive measures like self-reports fails, simply because the respondents cannot access their subconscious. Methods similar to the one used within neuroscience are available and give a direct link to the subconscious but the existing methods within this are expensive, invasive and impossible to use for people without special training within the field of neuroscience.

Initially this paper explains the importance of measuring emotions in the early stage before cognition kicks in and what influence emotions have on the visual system.

Then we turn on the light by introducing the new instrument Emotion Tool which enables us to find the keys. The paper briefly describes the principles of the patent pending emotion measurement system within Emotion Tool in the context of existing non-verbal instruments, comparing the measures done with Emotion Tool with measures done with GSR which is a well known and trusted method for measuring emotions – even though it is not widely used by researchers because of impracticality.

In addition to the walk through, a case is presented, in which immediate emotional responses and attention on print advertisement have been measured. The case will show how an effective use of computer science combined with psychophysiology realized in Emotion Tool can bring us closer to the human sub-conscious system. By quantifying early stage emotions and attention we will gain more knowledge about how the consumers and users engage in the designs and if the goals with our communication in the advertisement and product design are fulfilled.

Why measure emotion and attention?

We pay little attention to the large amount of visual information in the form of brands, products and ads we are exposed to every day and consider them of little importance to us. We believe that these exposures do not influence us considerably. In reality they influence us subconsciously through all our senses.

Even if we are not aware of it - visual attention is always active in processing the world around us. Many of these processes are automated and subconscious.

Earlier research within cognitive psychology and marketing research argued that an image, design, product or an ad would create thoughts that influenced our emotions and behavior. This view has later been turned around by modern brain science, which has proven that emotions and subconscious processes precede, guide and qualify attention, thoughts, memory and decision-making (Damasio, 1994). This is in line with the analytical psychology which argues that most of our behavior is based on emotions and subconscious processes, and that our conscious thoughts only account for about 10%. (Zaltman, 2003). Even just a short exposure to a brand triggers emotions in us that directly influence behavior even if we are not consciously aware of having seen the brand at all.

We now know that when we experience e.g. an ad, we react to it based on our conscious, cognitive interpretation and our subconscious, emotional configuration (Damasio, 1994). The experience is influenced by the stimulus itself, the context, as well as what is in our mind at that particular time. These elements determine how the ad will affect our behavior. If there is no emotional attachment and no visual impact, the stimuli will not catch our attention and get exposed to our cognitive mind. The perception of the stimulus will simply stay below the radar and only have a subconscious effect.

The behavioral impact from emotions

People are exposed to the same brands several times a day. Even if we have no recall or conscious memory of having seen these brands, if asked, they have been processed by our visual processing system - more specifically by the low-level attention. This is the part of attention that is automatic, involuntary and subconscious driven by emotions. Although we have no recall of it if asked, the information has been processed and has made an impact - and increased the brand awareness of the mega-brand. If being tested for recall, the results would be negative, but if tested for recognition - the result would be positive (Penn, 2007). The automated subconscious part of the visual system - the low-level attention has processed the logo.

Researchers at Duke University have found that brief, subliminal exposures (under the threshold of consciousness) to a well-known logo, have a much deeper impact than previously believed. Apple has consistently through 25 years associated the Apple logo with traits like creativity, originality and intelligent solutions. The research at Duke University showed that subliminal exposures to the Apple logo actually influenced the respondents to become more creative and original in a following problem solving task - and thus mirroring directly the brand traits (Chartrand et al., 2008). This study shows that subconscious processing of a logo (and obviously also brands and ads) is not only processed and stored, but also have a direct impact on behavior.

In other words; what we are exposed to has a subconscious impact that influence behavior directly. Even a short glimpse of a logo or an ad can directly influence behavior.

Emotions and visual processing

Besides having a direct impact on behavior the emotion system guides our sensory system particularly our visual system. The emotion system filters out an impressive amount of visual information, which is not relevant to us and guides the visual system towards the stimulus of relevance. This falls back to the body’s main function namely to keep the body out of trouble and in homeostasis. If the advertisement (stimulus) is relevant to us and has a high emotional impact it catches our attention and we become consciously aware of its existence. Because of the emotional reaction the mind is activated and the message gets pushed into the conscious part of the processing. That is why, some brands, advertisements and product designs immediately catch our attention to be explored, and others are being ignored. Some ads are able to hold our attention until we "get it", and this gives us an experience, with a certain emotional content. Some visual elements catch attention while others hold and direct attention (Calvo et al., 2004). There are two levels of attention - low-level attention and selective attention as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Timeline for visual processing.

Low-level attention is automated and subconsciously scans the whole visual field and spots the eye catchers - the visual elements that catch attention. Selective attention moves like a spotlight from one area of the visual field to another, analyzing the elements in more detail. Selective

attention moves according to some attention values being calculated from partly the stimulus itself and partly by what is in our mind, including emotions. Emotions participate in guiding and qualifying visual attention. Because of the subconscious nature of emotions they are manifested through physiological reactions spawned from the release of neurotransmitters and hormones.

Looking for the keys in the right place

Since these are subconscious processes, respondents cannot access them through rationalization. Surveys or focus groups are therefore not helpful measurement methods. We cannot ask people about emotions and the subconscious material simply because they have no conscious access to it. All that we can ask about is the feeling and the associations the ad produces. Feelings are the part of emotions that have become conscious (Damasio, 1994). The problem with this level is that it is indirect and influenced by thought (cognition). At this level associations, experience, group dynamics, psychological content, experienced demands and defense mechanisms, such as rationalizing and intellectualization, influence and disturb the reporting, thus making it very difficult to analyze the results. This is why much of the research within marketing and advertisement research, executed by the use of focus groups and surveys, might be of little value since it is not conscious, cognitive processing that underlies brand awareness, preferences, recognition and buying-decisions, but in fact emotions and subconscious processes. Processes, which are only accessible by measuring the changes in the brain and body that, are happening when emotions occur. New measurement methods are needed to access the subconscious level of information.

Within the relative new field of neuromarketing, the methods currently given most attention for measuring emotions are: fMRI, EEG and GSR. Neuromarketing is growing rapidly because of the possible consequences the above-mentioned research has on market research.

While subjective questionnaires may be relatively easy to administer but heavily influenced by cognitive interpretation and intellectualization, psycho-physiological and brain imaging techniques are extremely complex and difficult to use. The major drawback is small sample sizes, heavy time consumption and high complexity when analyzing, which makes the methods practically impossible to apply in any real world process. Because of the complexity, the results are often difficult to interpret and therefore the methods rarely deliver additional insight beyond existing methods unless spending weeks on analysis.

How do we gain access to emotions in a more convenient way?

New signal processing technology mixed with neuroscience and eye tracking allow us to look beyond these barriers. The non-intrusive technology that is sensitive enough to read the processes on the subconscious level and at the same time give us more insight on the conscious level is now available. The patent pending emotion and attention measurement system Emotion Tool can measure emotional response and visual attention from humans looking at images, using a method that is nonintrusive, reliable and valid. Encapsulated in Emotion Tool, advanced statistics, image processing and eye tracking, enable marketers to quantify emotions and visual attention, in an easy-to-use and time efficient way.

“Look into a person’s pupils he cannot hide himself“ (Confucius 551-478 B.C.)

Emotion Tool is a new instrument for assessing low level visual processing and selective attention by measuring and evaluating emotions. Eye feedback collected by monitoring pupil size, blink magnitudes and gaze behavior are analyzed and used to calculate an index of emotional reaction, using modern eye tracking equipment and unique software algorithms. Emotion Tool quantifies emotions and attention by analyzing physiological changes within eye gaze, eye blink and pupil dilation. Since eyes are parts of our brain hanging outside our heads they are the only part of our outer body, which can give some direct information of brain processes. One well-known parameter is pupil dilation as a result of changing light conditions, for the brain to most effectively process the outer world. The reactions of the eyes are in the same way affected by emotional and cognitive visual processing in different ways. Pupil dilation is related to emotional reactions. For example, pupil dilation has been coupled with activation of the sympathetic nervous system (Granholm & Steinhauer, 2004; Steinhauer et al., 1983). However, the relationship is complex because pupil size is also related to cognitive processing load (Beatty & Lucero-Wagoner, 2000; Staners et al., 1979) and the amount of light or hue in visual stimulus (Granholm & Steinhauer; 2004). Eye blink has also been related to emotional reactions, for example with defensive reactions like emotion-modulated eye blink startle (Bradley, et al., 1999, Dichter et al., 2002, Ruiz-Padial & Sollers, 2003). Finally, gaze patterns have been linked to emotional reactions (Calvo & Lang, 2004).

Improved precision by using an eye feedback method

Emotion Tool measures the above-mentioned subtle changes in the eyes and has shown to be four times more precise in measuring emotions than skin conductance (GSR). The iMotions emotion evaluation system embedded in Emotion Tool has been compared with galvanic skin response (GSR) measurements; a broadly used intrusive physiological measurement technique

for measuring emotional arousal. It has been found that the features collected by eye tracking, for physiological emotional response measurement, have a much smaller variation around the average than GSR amplitude response measurements. In fact, the coefficient of variation (c.v.) of the specific features used for assessing emotional arousal, is more than four times as high using GSR measurements than eye measurements. Consequently, data collected by eye tracking is much more reliable both in regard to the individual measurement and the average of the measurements, as opposed to using GSR measurements. Compared to GSR, Emotion Tool measures relatively weak emotional responses and more subtle emotions.

Automation in all parts of the non-intrusive test cycle

In addition to the higher resolution when measuring emotions, Emotion Tool also has the advantage that it is non intrusive (no equipment needs to be attached to the respondent) and discrete (the measurement tool is build into a computer screen). This makes the measurement setting more natural, and a more realistic testing scenario can be created. Another advantage is that the whole data collection, analysis and reporting is automated which allows large sample sizes to be tested fast and reliable and which provides the results within minutes.

Besides giving insights into the emotional aspect of an ad which will help investigating if the ad catch the attention, Emotion Tool also gives insight into the visual processing of the ad mapping out the visual selective attention of the ad. This is important information when validating the layout of visual elements in the design to se if the attention is split correctly between the different elements in a design. The eye movement is based on values given to the visual areas in the brain, invoked by the combination of the stimulus characteristics (color, contrast, shape) and what is in the respondents mind (thoughts, emotions, feelings).

The non-intrusive eye feedback test process

Measuring emotional response using Emotion Tool is very simple. The only requirements are a compliant eye tracker, a PC laptop and a controlled test environment. Once the stimuli and respondent information is entered the slideshow will be automatically set up and the test might begin. First there will be a gaze calibration on the respondent, after that a light calibration will be made (to be able to compensate for the light reflex while measuring pupil dilation). Finally an emotional baseline calibration of the respondent will be made; hereafter the stimuli will follow next in either a random or predetermined fashion as illustrated in Figure 2. All in all the test is very time efficient and immediately after the test is finished the results might be calculated in order to use the results in connection with other methods like a 1to1 interview. In total the test including the calibration procedures will take less than 10 minutes from the

respondent sits down in the chair and the results are ready (depending on the stimulus exposure time which is usually 6-10 seconds depending on the type of stimuli used).

Figure 2: Overview of the test phase in Emotion Tool.

The data collection, and emotional response and visual attention classification are completely automated processes that are handled by Emotion Tool the overview of the processing structure is illustrated in Figure 3. The emotional response will be displayed with a segment of ten or more respondents for statistical prudence. Visual attention measurement will be available if there is at least one valid respondent in the segment.

Validation of the eye feedback method

We have compared the arousal estimate of Emotion Tool against the broadly accepted emotional arousal estimate of the GSR technique. The results show that with 94% accuracy, almost all of the stimuli used in the comparison have been correctly classified for males. For females an accuracy of 83% of the stimuli are correctly classified. The highest correlation coefficient achieved in our comparison study is $\rho = 0.84$. With these results at hand there are strong indications that the emotion evaluation system embedded in Emotion Tool is at least as good an estimate of emotional arousal as GSR. Especially when we take into consideration that GSR measurements got a lower precision than Emotion Tool and that GSR is very vulnerable to small changes during the test e.g. the respondent moves.

Figure 3: Overview of the processing structure in Emotion Tool.

Emotion Tool usage case

The tool uncovers the visual attention processing and the emotional attention processing in different part of the process, because its intuitive, fast and efficient it can be used in the same ways as traditional non-psychophysiology approaches by all types of users who might benefit from having access to increased knowledge of the visual processing. Designers might use it to direct the design or the executives in a company use it to shorten the time it takes to make a decision between different campaign suggestions. Decisions they usually use a lot of time on because of fluffy facts. The results points out the ads with the weakest impact both on the attention and emotional side and delivers a clear indication on what to aim at the campaign. Figure 4 and 5 below displays some results showing the raw outcome of a test. From the results, the person who conducts the study – can easily derive the facts which the design team is interested in e.g.: In what designs do we have the most emotional impact? Does the segment react emotionally consistent across age? Does the product; functional description and brand gain any selective attention?

In Figure 4 (below) females' Emotional Involvement (arousal) is opposite to the reaction seen on males in Figure 5; Females react with more Emotional Involvement to Stimulus 1 than to Stimulus 2. Stimulus 1 only contains brand and product related elements with no aid from human models to attract attention. This indicates that females have a stronger relation to the shown product (in this case shoes) and brand than males do.

Figure 4: Results from Emotion Tool on a female segment (N=30).

In Figure 5 (below) males' Emotional Involvement (arousal) is significantly higher on Stimulus 2 compared to Stimulus 1. The total amount of Visual Attention on Stimulus 2 is higher than the similar stimulus on the female segment. This can be attributed to the presence of a partly naked female model in the stimulus. Only the brand and the model is attracting attention in Stimulus 2 - the product does not attract any attention.

Figure 5: Results from Emotion Tool on a male segment (N=30).

Common for both Males and Females is that the face of the human model attracts a lot of Visual Attention, even though the face is not giving any information about brand or product. However the way males and females prioritize the elements differ; For Stimulus 2 the males prioritize the female model higher than brand and product, by giving attention firstly to bodily features of the model and then to the brand – for females the pattern is opposite. Overall using Stimulus 2 would be a better choice if targeting both males and females in the campaign. The females get maximum exposure to both the brand and the product and the males get exposed to the brand. By using the ads with the highest emotional response the ads will more likely catch the attention from the competing ads.

Conclusion

As mentioned above, much of earlier emotion research and methods have failed due to the difficulty of addressing the subconscious nature of emotions in a convenient and precise way. This results in measuring only the cognitive visual processing and only getting a vague image of the emotional effect on the visual processing. The Emotion Tool measures the immediate emotional response and the selective attention. Which is at the pre-attention and pre-cognitive stage of the visual processing.

In the example above with the advertisement, a traditional approach to this would be to ask people what they thought of the commercial and invite people to a focus group. The results would only be reflecting the after effect of the processing, and only reflect a small fraction of what really goes on when the ads are processed. The Emotion Tool method gives an advantage to other measurements methods as it non-intrusive taps directly into the subconscious level, emotions and visual attention, presenting valuable information for analysis and design. As early stage emotions are critical for attention and behavior, this information is vital. In addition to that it provides the best from the traditional methods in regard to choice of sample size, flexibility and ease-of-use, and it provides the best from the neuroscience disciplines in form of objectivity, implicit measures and thereby less variability.

Let's turn on the light and look for the key inside the house instead of stumbling around in the streets looking for something, which is not there...

References

- Beatty, J. & Lucero-Wagoner, B. (2000): The pupillary system, in Caccioppo, J., Tassinari, L.G. & Berntson, G. (Eds.): *The Handbook of Psychophysiology*, Cambridge University Press, Hillsdale, New York.
- Bechara A, Damasio AR, Damasio H, Anderson SW (1994). "Insensitivity to future consequences following damage to human prefrontal cortex", *Cognition* 50: 7-15.
- Bradley, M. M., Cuthbert, B. N. & Lang, P. J. (1999): Affect and the startle reflex, in Dawson, M.E., Schell, A. & Boehmelt, A. (Eds.): *Startle modification: Implications for neuroscience, cognitive science and clinical science*, Stanford University Press, Stanford, 242–276.
- Calvo, M. G., & Lang, P. J. (2004). Gaze patterns when looking at emotional pictures: Motivationally biased attention. *Motivation and Emotion*, 28, 221–243.
- Dichter, G.S., Tomarken, A.J. & Baucom, B.R. (2002): Startle modulation before, during and after exposure to emotional stimuli, *International Journal of Psychophysiology*, 43, 191-196
- Damasio, A.R. (1994): *Descartes Error - Emotion, Reason, and the Human Brain*, G.P. Putnam's Sons, New York
- Granholm, E. & Steinhauer, S.R. (2004): Pupillometric Measures of Cognitive and Emotional Processes, *International Journal of Psychophysiology*, 52, 1–6
- Hugdahl, K. (2001): *Psychophysiology: The Mind-body Perspective*, Harvard University Press
- Penn, D. (2007). *Brain Science: In Search of the Emotional Unconscious*. In *Marketing Research Handbook*. ESOMAR. 2007.
- Ruiz-Padial, L., Sollers, J.J., Vila, J. & Thayer, J.F. (2003): The rhythm of the heart in the blink of an eye: Emotion-modulated startle magnitude covaries with heart rate variability, *Psychophysiology*, 40, 306–313
- Staners, R.F., Coulter, M., Sweet, A.W. & Murphy, P. (1979): The papillary response as an indicator of arousal and cognition, *Motivation and Emotion*, 3 (4), 319-340
- Steinhauer, S. R., Boller, F., Zubin, J. & Pearlman, S. (1983): Pupillary dilation to emotional visual stimuli revisited, *Psychophysiology*, 20
- Chartrand, T, Fitzsimons, G., (2008): Automatic Effects of Brand Exposure on Motivated Behavior: How Apple Makes You “Think Different”. In Press
- Zaltman, G. (2003): *How Customers Think: Essential Insights into the Mind of the Market*, Harvard Business School Press

iMotions - Emotion Technology A/S

<http://www.imotionsglobal.com>, ‘iMotions’ and ‘Emotion Tool’ are trademarks of iMotions.